

ANALYSIS OF THE ENTERPRISING SPIRIT IN ORDER TO CREATE A COMPANY SUCCESSFULLY BY MEANS OF A FUZZY EXPERT SYSTEM

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Abstract

This paper has as main objective the design and construction of a fuzzy expert system which has been designed with eminently practical character, and which offers a diligent attention to the user, through the help of a guided decisional strategy with the final purpose of helping him to define his possible enterprising profile in order to create his own Company, having previously evaluated his initial capacities as prognosis of success, through an exhaustive study on the personality of the individual, his psychological and sociological characteristics (needs of profits, leadership, orientation by intuition more than by common sense, propensity to take risks, and so on), and thus, it is finalized advising him about how suitable is creating his own private enterprise to make a guessed right decision.

Key words: Database, Fuzzy Expert System, Computer Application, Entrepreneurs

I. INTRODUCTION

The entrepreneur is a person who perceives the opportunity that the market offers and has the motivation, the impulse and the ability to mobilize resources in order to find this opportunity. In addition, studies on the lives of entrepreneurs have demonstrated many times that the enterprising spirit decreases because of the success.

In defining a desirable educational structure, we should take into account the initial conditions and experience of the most developed studies about it, because the search of a profession, which fits to the qualities of the person, requires a full knowledge of oneself. So, it is necessary help him to clarify and to consider the interests, individual characteristics and the qualities, as well as to differentiate between vocation and profession, in order to choose a profession with realism, because it is necessary to have a better knowledge of oneself to understand with more

precision the actions that correspond with the professional orientation and vocational guidance, by means of the evaluation of the vocational interests, behaviors, aptitudes, attitudes, personal characteristics and person's values, that qualify him to the professional profile that he wishes.

In this sense, speaking about vocation is speaking of ourselves, of ours uneasiness, anxieties, worries, tastes and objectives, it is subjective and internal and it must be chosen by means of the knowledge of oneself, and, on the other hand, the profession refers to something external, it is action, and it is which allows us to satisfy our vocation, and it must be chosen in the better possible way, by means of an evaluation of elements like vocational and professional areas, profile of studies, specific characteristics of each university, resources that offers, and so on.

The model is organized by specific contents in different modules that allows to evaluate the behavior, differentiating aptitudes and attitudes in each one of them. The software product is outlined as an application that works on a database and that offers to the user a graphical interface that allows him to use the information in a fast and easily understandable way.

The utility of the developed model is, among others, for students of last courses in theirs studies, and in general, to any person who wishes knowing his possibilities of success as entrepreneur. The application fulfills demanding requirements as response times, robustness, manageability, reliability, correction, and so on.

II. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this paper is to show the possibility of introducing fuzzy logic in order to serve as a helpful element in studies about the analysis of the possible enterprising profile of each person to choose the creating of his own company as profession.

The development of the present model has been tried to include the greater number of possible variables with incidence in the exit variable, in order that it is possible to be analyzed like a complete model.

So, this work tries to describe the process of building an Expert System, which offers a personal attention and solution that allows to orient to the individual in terms of choosing a profession, designing, therefore, a decisional strategy and which pretends, among others, to obtain the following objectives:

- It allows to the individual to evaluate his capacities as prognosis of success in the professional area of creating his Company or Enterprise. Thus, it helps him to take a good decision, because it allows having a better knowledge of himself, by means of the evaluation of his behavior, aptitudes and attitudes. Therefore, the individual can know if he is qualified to the professional profile that he wishes.

- It helps to the individual to see the differences between vocation and profession.

By all it, this Fuzzy Expert System has been designed to describe the implementation of knowledge acquisition and corresponding reasoning tools in an expert system educational within the domain of choosing a profession in terms of establishing an enterprise.

III. CREATION OF COMPANIES

The Professional Profiles arise as way to develop the different aptitudes, necessary capacities and abilities in the worker to carry out his profession, job's condition, professional risks, A set of actions are defined to support to any person (students finishing their studies, workers not satisfied with their professional performance or that have discovered that their job is not as they thought it was).

In a socioeconomic reality, in which the employment is a scarce good, or at least, it is not enough for all people, the self-employment comes being a professional exit. The creation of the own job is a selection, perhaps the hardest one, and for that reasons, the most satisfactory in a half or long-term.

The self-employment is an option within the incorporation to the labor market.

IV. ANALYSIS OF THE ENTERPRISING SPIRIT BY MEANS OF A FUZZY EXPERT SYSTEM

Fuzzy controllers appears as the best means of processing and implementing uncertain human experience, these controllers are normally applied to human controlled processes. Fuzzy control and supervision enables means of converting linguistic strategy based on expert knowledge into an automatic strategy. The fuzzy controller consists of a set of fuzzy rules that describe the control strategy of an operator. The rules take the form of: IF (set of conditions) THEN (set of consequences).

Fuzzy control offers, in general, wide possibilities for tackling decision problems in a lot of different areas. Specifically, fuzzy control methods are very useful when the processes are too complex to be analyzed by conventional quantitative means, or when the available sources are interpreted in a qualitative, imprecise or uncertain way. But it needs of experts to establish a control strategy. The basic configuration of a fuzzy controller consists of:

- The fuzzyfying interface: That measures the process variables, scaling of such, transferring the value range to the corresponding data universe. These variables (fuzzy variables stored in the database) are defined by a set of labels each one representing a function defined over the domain of its variable. As is well known, Zadeh (1965), using Fuzzy logic, introduced

the concept of linguistic quantifier to represent the large number of possible quantifiers, he suggested that the semantic of a linguistic quantifier may be captured by using fuzzy subsets for its representation. In this paper we have used form-based interfaces. Initially, the user has to insert all necessary data for the analysis of the enterprising profile of the person, thus, the system's data base is created. This data base can be stored so that it can be retrieved, changed or enriched easily in the future. Once all the necessary data are inserted, during the evaluation procedure of the system will seek in the knowledge base for a rule including in its conclusions part the performance of the examined data, then it checks the conditions of that rule in an attempt to satisfy the rule. The necessary information concerning the qualitative criteria is acquired from the database or through an interactive dialogue between the user and the expert system. Firstly, the variables, which are relevant and therefore need to be taken into account in the analysis process, should be established.

- The defuzzifying interface: Consisting of converting into linguistic values (which may be considered as fuzzy sets). It performs the scaling duty, transforming the reference universe into variable ranges acting on the process and the defuzzifying which a non fuzzy control act produces as a result of a fuzzy inference.
- The knowledge base: Which contains the operator knowledge and the control objectives, consisting of a database containing the fuzzy set definitions, and the fuzzy rules, which govern the control actions.
- The decision making logic: That makes up the nucleus of the fuzzy system, and it has the ability of simulating human reasoning, using the rules of fuzzy logic system. The decision making process can be defined as the study of how decision are actually made and how they can be made better or more successfully.

V. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM

The development of the model has been carried out under the vague or uncertain hypothesis of information, since the opinions expressed by the end user of the program about the excellent variables for the decision model are more easily evaluated by means of Fuzzy valuations. In this sense, we have included a total of 36 Fuzzy variables (creative, disciplined, ambitious, motivating, work as a team, shelf-sacrificing, constant, exigent, active, imaginative, realistic, leadership, fighter, determined, self-esteem, innovator, responsible, shelf-confidence, decisive, planner, with capacity to take risks, and to face up problems, etc.). For each of them, their possible states are determined by means of linguistics labels, and also the range of each of the representative fuzzy subgroups of such states.

Later, the degree of each of the linguistics labels of each variable is really determined by fuzzy rules of production. In order to handle and to interpret this great amount of information, the application works on a database of Microsoft Access and displays a graphical interface easily understandable to the user. The model has explained helps by each field or variable to inform, and all the process is based on different queries, causing that the code generation is minimum, and it makes easy the direct reusability of this application as well as its extension in other later ones. It would only be necessary to transport the wished queries, in addition, it can be directly converted to later versions. Therefore, you can manage the understanding and later maintenance of the application by any final user, not demanding great computer science nor technicians knowledge of the program. Also, this implementation contributes to the model the advantages of robustness, reusability, correction and facility of understanding, maintenance, adaptability to changes, easily modifiable, easy of using and easy of integrating in other applications.

The variables which are showed in figure 1 are grouped to consider of the individual characteristics in: Variables of Entry (academic, professional experience and personal characteristics of the individual), Variables Intermediate and Variables of Exit.

Figure 1.

By means of rules of production designed to the effect, which will carry out all the combinations that there are among the variables of entry to obtain the intermediate variables (determining the values of the intermediate variable's linguistics terms), and between intermediate variables to obtain new variables in successive levels that the expert has defined.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODEL

The basic points followed for the development of the model can be made specific in the following ones:

- Definition of Models
- Definition of Labels of State of Variables of Models
- Definition of Variables of Models
- Definition of States of Variables of Models
- Definition of Relations of dependency between variables of model
- Definition of the Rules of the Models.

As far as the use of the developed model, in Figure 2 is displayed a form with variables of entry that must be informed all of them compulsorily.

Variable	Value
Ambicioso	5
Inconformista	8
Creativo	7
Disciplinado	4
Conocimiento de Mercado	1
Admite consejos	10
Flexible	8
Motivador	8
Trabajo en equipo	6
Sacrificado	2
Constante	7
Exigente	9
Activo	7
Visión de Futuro	3
Imaginativo	7
Miedo a lo que pueda ocurrir	9
Afronta problemas	10
Recursos Propios	2000000

¿Tiene OBJETIVOS que van más allá de sus posibilidades?
¿Lucharía por tener un mayor nivel económico?
¿Y por tener un mayor poder?
¿Piensa en mejorar su situación a todos los niveles?

Figure 2.

Each variable has three possible labeled states of which it will only be in one of them, and by means of the numerical value given to that variable it will be associated to one of those 3 states. The user can use an interactive system of help to value each field –located in all the different fields that have to be filled up–, which inquires to him on the meaning of each field, its possible values and ranges, and it lets him show the definition of states of that variable

(their fuzzy numbers, which at first are hidden to the user). Finally, the system will show the result of his possible entrepreneur spirit, through a similar screen, which figure 3 shows.

Figure 3.

This way concludes the study of the enterprising profile of the individuals. Another added functionality is the possibility of acceding to two interesting queries that will have been generated and that will give the Fuzzification and later Defuzzification of the Variable of Exit of the Model that has been executed.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

At the present time there are no any model with which the individual can autoevaluate himself his possible enterprising profile. With the development of this work we have been able to contribute, by means of the construction of a Fuzzy Expert system, to the design an instrument to analyze the enterprising profile of a person. With an implementation of easy handling for any user no very used with the computer science and that directly allows to be modifiable or re-usable in possible future lines. It supposes, therefore, the principle of the computerization of this field of Orientation for the person and the improvements that can be made are enormous.

VIII. LINE FUTURE

It can be easily extended and applied to approach the reality of the labour market to the educative scope, showing that in the mass media many professional profiles have room, and therefore, personal characteristic and very different studies, provide to each participant his own orientation advice, offer a huge updated information service on academic option and professional exits, and to make the society conscious of the importance of the Orientation Professional like key of the future of our youth, showing the preoccupation and the activity of the economical agents and trends social to obtain a good preparation for active life throughout the period of schooling.

By all it, easily it could be extended:

- To offer to the professional a customized, systematic and coherent Orientation with his profile, that allows his maximum personal and professional development, an effective Orientation of his career professional, to make more suitable formative actions.
- To offer to the company an active system of information of the workers on their level of qualification, potentiality and development of their professional career, and to manage with all the excellent information on the evolution of the professions and the contents of the jobs. Therefore, the individual will be allowed:
 1. Knowledge of himself: To identify his aptitudes, values, interests and personal characteristics, to clarify if he is satisfied with their actual profile.
 2. Knowledge of the environment: Analyzing different characteristic of each profession on the basis that each individual can prepare his professional profile before deciding to study a certain university studies or other studies of Formation. They would have:
 - to know the characteristics and variables group of the different professions,
 - to compare the different areas from knowledge and the professions that conform them,
 - to identify and to evaluate the requirements of entrance, course and culmination of the professions of their interest,
 - to differentiate the opportunities that offer diverse occupational atmospheres and
 - to investigate the present labour market.
 3. Taking of decisions: Designing a possible decisional strategy to help him to process his professional profile, to integrate the elements of the knowledge of himself, and to justify the options of selection with base in the variables considered in the previous point.

The knowledge-based system expert consists of a database subsystem and a knowledge acquisition subsystem, and it is appropriate by the following reasons:

- Shells are fast and provide reliable response times.
- Shells always have the capability for reasoning about the behavior of data.
- Shells are very easy to integrate with the external hardware and conventional software.
- Shells can adapt to changes in workload or resource availability.

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